

Smarandache Sociological Theory:

As in the Primitive Society, the modern society is making for MATRIARCHATE - the woman leads in the industrialized societies.

From an authoritarian PATRIARCHATE in the Slavery and Feudalism towards a more democratic MATRIARCHATE at present. The sexuality plays an immense role in the manipulation of men by women, because the women "have monopoly of the sex" as was justifying to me an American friend kept by his wife henpecked!

A cyclic social development.

The woman becomes the center of the society's cell, the family.

The sexual pleasure influences different life circles, from the low class people to the leading spheres. Freud was right... One uses women in espionage, in influencing politicians' decisions, in attracting businessmen - by their feminine charms, who obtain faster results than their male proponents.

The women have more rights than men in western societies (in divorce trials).

Reference:

Smarandache, Florentin, "Neutrosophy. / Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic", American Research Press, Rehoboth, 1989.